

Spectrophotometric Determination of Fe(II), Co(II), Ru(III) and Ir(III) with 5-Nitroso-2, 4,6-Triaminopyrimidine

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A sensitive reagent 5-nitroso-2,4,6-triaminopyrimidine is proposed for spectrophotometric determination of iron(II), cobalt(II), ruthenium(III) and iridium(III). The optimum conditions for the determination have been established. The toleration limits of many diverse ions, which can co-exist during the determinations are found.

A number of pyrimidine derivatives have been recently introduced as reagents¹⁻⁴ for spectrophotometric determination of iron- and platinum-group metals. The enhanced electronic effect at adjacent positions with respect to annular nitrogen atoms in the pyrimidine molecule and the presence of suitable chelating groups make them attractive analytically. The compounds are inexpensive and available commercially. Their solutions in dilute acids are stable for a long time. In the present communication, the analytical potentialities of 5-nitroso-2, 4, 6-triaminopyrimidine (I) are described. The reagent is subsequently used in spectrophotometric

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determination of iron(II), cobalt(II), ruthenium(III) and iridium(III). In sensitivity, it ranks amongst the most sensitive reagents.

Experimental

Standard solutions of the ligand, iron(II), cobalt(II), ruthenium(III) and iridium(III) were prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of 5-nitroso-2, 4, 6-triaminopyrimidine (K & K Laboratories, U. S. A.) in 0.02 N HCl, Mohr's salt and $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in double distilled water and $\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 1.0 N HCl. The solutions were standardized before use.

The pH of the solutions were adjusted with acetate buffers and dilute solutions of NaOH and HCl. All other reagents used were of analytical grade. The deionized water was used throughout the work.

Absorbance readings were taken with a Unicam SP-600 spectrophotometer. For pH measurements, a Metrohm pH-meter type E-350 was used.

Determination of iron (II) : To a suitable aliquot of iron(II) solution (Table 1), add sufficient excess of the reagent followed by 2.0 ml of 2.0 M sodium acetate solution. Adjust the pH, dilute the solution to 10.0 ml and measure the absorbance at 640 nm against reagent blank. Calculate the amount of the metal from a precalibrated graph.

Determination of cobalt(II) or iridium(III) : To cobalt(II) or iridium(III) solution containing requisite amount of the metal (Table 1), add the reagent solution in excess, adjust the pH and make up the volume. Note the absorbance at λ_{max} of the complex vs. reagent blank. Calculate the amount of the metal by comparing the absorbance with a calibrated curve.

Determination of ruthenium(III) : To ruthenium (III) solution (containing 10.0-40.0 μg of the metal), add 2.5 ml of 0.01 M reagent solution (in 0.02 N HCl) and 4.0 ml of acetate buffer to adjust pH around 1.8. Heat the solution on a steam bath for 90 min., cool and dilute it to 10.0 ml. Measure the absorbance of the red complex at 510 nm against a reagent blank. Calculate the amount of ruthenium by comparing with a standard graph drawn under identical conditions.

TABLE I—CHARACTERISTICS OF THE COMPLEXES

Characteristics	Fe(II)-complex	Co(II)-complex	Ru(III)-complex	Ir(III)-complex
Colour	Blue	Yellow	Red	Yellow
λ_{max} (nm)	640	380	510	375
ϵ_{max} (l. mole ⁻¹ .cm ⁻¹)	2.0×10^4	1.4×10^4	1.9×10^4	4.0×10^3
Reagent needed for full colour development (titration method)	80-molar concentration	30-Molar concentration	50-Molar concentration	60-Molar concentration
pH range to attain maximum absorbance	6.6-8.0	4.6-6.5	1.1-3.5	4.5-7.0
Molar composition (metal : ligand) by continuous variations and logarithmic methods	1 : 3	1 : 3	1 : 2	1 : 3
Behaviour in organic solvents	Not Extractable	Not Extractable	Not Extractable	Not Extractable
Beer's law range (ppm)	Up to 2.2	Up to 2.4	Up to 5.0	Up to 40.0
Accurate range of determination (ppm)	0.6-2.0	0.6-2.0	1.0-4.0	5.0-30.0
Sandell's sensitivity	0.0028	0.0042	0.0053	0.048
Standard deviation (calculated from 8 samples)	0.0046	0.0035	0.0025	0.0056

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF FOREIGN IONS

Tolerance limits (ppm) in determination of

Foreign ion	Iron (1.4 ppm)	Cobalt (1.5 ppm)	Ruthenium (2.5 ppm)	Iridium (19.2 ppm)
F ⁻ ; Cl ⁻	50; 500	200; 2000	2000; 10000	1000; 10000
Br ⁻ ; I ⁻	1000; 1000	2000; 2000	10000; 1000	1000; 500
CN ⁻ ; NO ₂ ⁻	Int.; 100	Int.; 10	Int.; 20	Int.; Int.
NO ₃ ⁻ ; ClO ₄ ⁻	100; 1000	100; 10000	200; 10000	100; 10000
CNS ⁻ ; CH ₃ COO ⁻	50; 10000	150; 100	500; 10000	Int.; 10000
SO ₄ ²⁻ ; S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻	10000; 20	10000; 50	10000; 1000	1000; Int.
C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻ ; Tartrate	10; 80	10; 50	1000; 10000	20; 50
Thiourea; EDTA	20; Int.	50; Int.	Int.; 1000	Int.; 100
BO ₃ ³⁻ ; PO ₄ ³⁻	100; 100	100; 100	10000; 10000	50; 25
Citrate	10	10	200	20
Cu ²⁺ ; Ag ⁺	5; 20*	10; 50*	10; 50*	5; 20*
Ca ²⁺ or Sr ²⁺	10000	10000	10000	10000
Ba ²⁺ ; Zn ²⁺	10000; 50	10000; 100	10000; 120	1000; 10
Cd ²⁺ ; Hg ²⁺	50; 20**	150; 200**	200; 200**	20; 25**
Al ³⁺ ; Sn ⁴⁺	60; 50	100; 10	100; 10	50; Int.
Pb ²⁺ ; V ⁴⁺	20; 5	100; 10	100; Int.	20; Int.
Mn ²⁺ ; Fe ³⁺	10; Int.	30; Int.	50; 30	25; Int.
Co ²⁺ ; Ni ²⁺	4; 5	—; 5	10; 50	25; Int.
Ru ³⁺ ; Rh ³⁺	1; 5	1; 1	—; 10	Int.; 2
Pd ²⁺ ; Os ⁸⁺	Int.; Int.	Int.; 5	20; 15	Int.; Int.
Ir ³⁺ ; Pt ⁴⁺	Int.; Int.	Int.; 10	40; 50	—; Int.

Int. means interferes; *Masked with Cl⁻; **Masked with I⁻

In case when the foreign ion was precipitated as hydrated oxide, it was centrifuged off, washed and the solution brought up to the volume.

Results

Light red coloured reagent solution exhibits λ_{max} at 230, 275, 325 and 530 nm with molar absorptivities of 6600, 6020, 17280 and 100 respectively. As its absorption is appreciable at λ_{max} of its metal complexes, it was therefore used as blank throughout the study. The solution is fairly stable for a week at room temperature (30°). It can, however, be preserved in a cool place for 5-6 weeks without noticeable decomposition. The spectral characteristics of its metal complexes are summarized in Table 1. The sensitivity of the reagent for the metals is of high order. The adequate pH range exists in which determination can be made. From the toleration limits found for diverse ions (Table 2), it is evident that excess of many ions can coexist during determination of small amounts of the metals. The complex formation was instantaneous except in case of ruthenium when the solution was heated on a steam bath for at least 75 min. However,

the continued heating for 4 hr. did not affect the absorbance.

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